

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

UDC 621.039.5

FEATURES OF THE THERMAL PLUTONIUM EFFECT AND DYNAMICS OF THE ACCIDENT AT UNIT III OF THE FUKUSHIMA 1 NUCLEAR POWER PLANT

Tarasov V.A.,
Chernezhenko S.A.,
Korduba I.B.,
Vashchenko V.N.

*Odesa National Polytechnic University, Odesa, Ukraine;
Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture;
Interdepartmental Center for Fundamental Research
in the field of energy and ecology*

Abstract

Before the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) accident, the prospect of expanding the nuclear power plants fuel base was also associated with the use of MOX fuel (mixed oxide uranium-plutonium fuel). The Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident, which has led to the reactor core meltdown, revealed an insufficient knowledge of the fuel nuclides temperature properties in a temperature range wider than the operating temperatures ranges of existing reactors (above 1000 K).

The paper presents the results of calculating the temperature dependences of the fission and radiative capture nuclear reactions cross-sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum for uranium 238, uranium 235 and plutonium 239. A fundamental difference in the temperature dependences of the uranium 235 and plutonium 239 nuclear reactions cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum is found and explained for the studied temperature range. The temperature dependences of the heat sources densities for MOX fuel and uranium oxide fuel for thermal reactors are calculated as well.

For the first time, the fundamental difference between the temperature dependences of the heat sources densities for the MOX fuel and uranium oxide fuel is shown.

The accident dynamics theory based on the fundamental difference in the temperature dependences of the heat sources densities for the MOX fuel and oxide uranium fuel is presented. It allows to identify and explain several characteristic temperature features of the accident dynamics at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant Unit 3, where one third of the reactor fuel load was MOX-fuel.

Keywords: Fukushima Daiichi NPP 1 severe beyond design basis accident, thermal reactors, core meltdown, MOX fuel, uranium oxide fuel, plutonium 239, accident dynamics.

1. Introduction

The most important tasks of the further nuclear energy development strategy include ensuring the safe operation of nuclear power plants, fuel base expansion and spent nuclear fuel reprocessing.

All operating nuclear reactors and even the latest advanced reactors, including the so-called Generation IV reactors, are fundamentally dangerous, since they all have a supercritical fuel load that ensures their campaign duration, and the chain reaction is maintained using a control system that regulates the reactor reactivity. And only now the development of nuclear reactors fundamentally differing from the previous generations reactors, which do not have a super critical load of nuclear fuel and do not require the reactor reactivity regulation, is carried out. The authors classify these nuclear reactors as the Generation V reactors.

The safety requirements for the new Generation V reactors are fully met by the wave uranium-plutonium reactor of L.P.Feoktistov (also called in the USA as "Traveling-wave reactor" and in Japan as "CANDLE" reactor) characterized by internal safety [1-52]. This new type of a reactor also allows to eliminate the nuclear fuel enriching procedure in the nuclear fuel cycle

and to use in it the natural (and even technical) uranium, i.e., spent nuclear fuel.

At the same time, the wave reactor dynamics is the open physical system dynamics, which is described by the nonlinear dynamics theory, i.e., is characterized by several features that are fundamental for the nonlinear dissipative structures theory. One of those is the uranium-plutonium fissile medium nonequilibrium under conditions of neutron field high densities and high temperatures. It should be also noted that in the wave nuclear reactors a strong change of the fuel nuclide composition occurs, e. g., under the appropriate modes of wave neutron-nuclear burning in a uranium-plutonium fuel medium, the burnup of uranium 238 may exceed 70 % of its initial concentration, and plutonium 239 may be completely absent initially. This fundamentally distinguishes the wave nuclear reactors from the previous generations reactors, in which operating modes are implemented using the reactor control system, in which a fuel burnup is about 4 %-6 % per a campaign, that is, the fuel composition practically does not change, and the neutron flux density and temperature are not high (e. g., for VVER F~10¹³ ÷ 10¹⁴ n/(cm² s) and T ≈280°C).

The basic kinetics of a wave reactor (the neutrons and nuclides kinetics) are connected by direct and inverse relationships with the kinetics of heat transfer and radiation-induced fuel defects [59; 60]. The fuel defects kinetics affects the reactor reactivity through a geometric dimensions change caused by plastic deformation, swelling or destruction of fuel under load and irradiation, as well as through its density change. The dissipative thermal structures formation and temperature nonlinear modes with Kurdumov blow-up implementation [44, 45, 47-49] or the dissipative structures formation of uranium-plutonium fissile medium defects can significantly affect the reactor kinetics, mainly, the very implementation and stability of the slow nuclear burning wave in a reactor.

The hypothesis of a wave-type georeactor located at the boundary of the liquid and solid Earth's cores also requires that its kinetics should be studied at temperatures from 5000 K to 7000 K [37].

Before the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident, the prospect of the NPP fuel base expanding was also associated with the use of the MOX fuel (mixed oxide uranium-plutonium fuel).

The Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident, which has led to the Generation III reactors core meltdown, revealed insufficient knowledge of the temperature properties of fuel nuclides in a wider temperature range (exceeding 1000 K) than the operating temperature ranges of existing reactors.

The paper authors' previous works, in which the temperature properties of the reactor fuel fissile media were studied, e. g. [44, 45, 47-51], were mainly focused on the temperature features of the wave neutron-nuclear burning processes.

After the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident, several papers were published, e. g., [52-53], in which the peculiar temperature properties of the thermal nuclear reactors fuel nuclides were associated with the possible features of the accident development at the Fukushima Daiichi NPP Unit 3. However, this was performed very carefully, in the form of conjectural hypotheses since there were very few physical data on the Fukushima Daiichi accident itself. The paper [58] was almost entirely devoted to nonlinear temperature blow-up modes in fissile media, but their possible connection with the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident dynamics features was given only a brief mention.

However, today, years after the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident, some data have appeared, albeit in a very meager volume and, unfortunately, published not in scientific journals, but in the media, confirming the authors' theoretical assumptions. The paper [49] was mainly focused just on the accident features. Thus, the decision was made to publish it, apparently, because of the lack of other publications on this topic in scientific journals and due to the fact that the paper was given attention in the electronic media, e. g., in [54], which in itself was a rarity for scientific papers, and in [55] posted on the Internet website and available to a wide range of readers interested in the accident causes and consequences, which was evidently of considerable public interest for obvious reasons.

Indeed, in [55] there is a section titled "Fukushima plutonium effect", which is almost entirely based on the statement in [40] about a possible connection between the features of the accident at the Fukushima Daiichi NPP Unit 3 with nonlinear temperature blow-up modes in uranium-plutonium fissile environments. However, this chapter is supplemented with an important Figure 21 [55, 56], which is a video recording of the Fukushima Daiichi NPP Unit 3 accident dynamics with its analysis and conclusions made by the nuclear reactors designer Setsuo Fujiwara in [57, 58]. The video indicates that there were three explosions, which could be heard when the video was played back slowly. The first was an explosion of hydrogen formed as a result of the steam-zirconium reaction of water decomposition, to which the smoke white color corresponds in the video; the orange color of the burning flame above the Unit 3 reactor indicated a very high temperature of ~ 3000 K, that is, the melting point of the reactor oxide fuel during the second explosion; and the third explosion, accompanied by black smoke, indicated an explosion in the uranium-plutonium fuel medium and its release. Setsuo Fujiwara [57,58] believed that the second explosion was caused not by a hydrogen explosion, but by the reactor rapid transition to a supercritical state, that is, by its acceleration on prompt neutrons due to a temperature and pressure increase inside the reactor vessel, which resulted in the boiling bubbles collapse. Such process led to the reactor reactivity increase because the void reactivity coefficient was negative, and therefore Setsuo Fujiwara called the accident at Unit 3 a nuclear explosion.

It should be noted that, as will be seen below in this paper, the independent expert's conclusion in [57,58] about the neutron runaway of the Unit 3 reactor was an important argument in favor of the authors' theory, which initially assumed the presence of neutrons.

In [59, 60], experimental data are presented from [61] on measuring the radioactive isotope sulfur-35 concentration in sulfate aerosols and in gaseous sulfur dioxide in the oceanic air in the La Jolla Village on the Pacific Beach of California, based on which it was concluded that ocean water was irradiated by neutrons with a fluence of 4×10^{11} n/m², since the sulfur-35 radionuclides were formed in ocean water containing chlorine-35 during neutron irradiation.

It is worthy of mention that in both [55] and [57,58] the assumption was made about the Unit 3 reactor fuel melting, which also testified in favor of nuclear reactions involving neutrons, since due to the chemical reactions it would hardly be possible to heat up to melting points and melt such an amount of oxide fuel.

In the paper [62] it was reported that TEPCO (Tokyo Electric Power Company) published the results of a month-long study that began on February 12, 2015, in the Unit 1 reactor building in collaboration with the International Research Institute for Nuclear Decommissioning (IRID). The two companies collected the experiment data from its inception to March 10. The project used cosmic rays to view the building interior [63, 64]. Analyzing the muons flux generated by elementary particles during cosmic rays colliding with the atmosphere,

TEPCO was able to generate an X-ray image of the reactor interior. Muons can pass through concrete and iron, but they get blocked and change direction, when collide with the high-density materials such as plutonium and uranium, creating a "shadow" on the X-ray image. According to the study, TEPCO stated that the fuel has melted because there was no shadow around the reactor core, i.e., that the fuel was not where it should be, which indicated that the fuel was likely to have been melted and "moved down." The operator also reported that there was not any water accumulation in the reactor pressure vessel core and that it was possible that fuel fragments were in the spent fuel pool, but their sizes would be calculated later. TEPCO also said that the results confirmed the previous assumptions about the fuel meltdown. They planned to continue measurements until enough data should be obtained to conduct a statistical analysis and to get a possibility for the obtained data use in determining the fuel masses configuration. This would allow the work plan development for their removal. Perhaps the removal would be performed by robots due to the high radiation doses in the reactor.

Thus, in [62] the first experimental evidence of the reactor core melting is presented.

Consequently, today enough data is already available to reasonably assert that the accidents have developed in accordance with a theoretical model based on the dynamics of nuclear reactions involving neutrons, since due to chemical reactions it would hardly be possible to heat up to melting temperatures and melt such an amount of oxide fuel.

Therefore, in compliance with the foregoing, this paper presents the results of a theoretical study of the reactor fuel nuclides temperature properties in a wide temperature range (above 1000 K) and the temperature dependences of the heat sources densities for MOX fuel (a mixture of uranium and plutonium 239 dioxides) and oxide uranium fuel (a mixture of uranium 238 and uranium 235 dioxides) aiming to identify the possible differences between these dependences, as well as to identify and explain several characteristic temperature features of the accident at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant Unit 3, where one third of the reactor fuel load was the MOX fuel.

To summarize, it should be noted that the text relating to wave nuclear reactors and the nonlinear dynamics of wave neutron-nuclear burning is included at the beginning of the introduction to this paper not by chance, since to explain the dynamics features of the destroyed nuclear reactors nuclear fuel during the accident, after it and up to the present is possible using the dynamics of wave burning, temperature blow-up modes, and radiation defects dissipative structures in nuclear fuel.

2. Theory.

Firstly, let us first note that the theoretical model, on which the hypothesis of the accident development at Fukushima Daiichi Unit 3 presented in the article is based, is a development and addition to the model, the development, and study of which we began earlier, for example, in works [56-62] and are still under way.

However, all of our previous works only mentioned the accident at Fukushima Daiichi Unit 3 and suggested the possible contribution of the aggravation modes to this accident.

2.1. Dependences on the reactor fuel temperature for the cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum.

Since the accident at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant occurred at BWR reactors (boiling water reactors having the thermal neutron spectrum), this paper presents the results of the temperature dependences calculations obtained for the nuclear fission and radiative capture reactions cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum for uranium 238, uranium 235 and plutonium 239. It is known that the neutrons energy spectrum in thermal reactors differs from the Maxwellian spectrum due to its non-equilibrium because in the reactor core the neutrons formation processes during nuclear fission (with the neutron energies being distributed over the fission spectra for fissile nuclides), as well as the neutron moderation and absorption processes take place all the time. As a rigorous theory of neutron moderation in a reactor fuel fissile medium, which could naturally include neutron thermalization, does not exist, the model approximations use for estimating the neutron spectra is necessary. The most widely used approach is based on the neutron gas model assuming that thermalized neutrons are distributed over the Maxwellian distribution energies, but not at the core fissile medium temperature, but at the neutron gas temperature. In this case, the effect of absorption or insufficient moderation in the medium on the spectrum shift from the "pure" Maxwell is evaluated using the input temperature of the neutron gas given by the following semi-empirical expression [65, 66]:

$$T_{NG} = T * \left[1 + 1,4 * \Sigma_a(kT) / \xi \Sigma_s(1eV) \right], \quad (1)$$

where T is the fissile medium temperature; Σ_a is the macroscopic (thermal) cross section of the medium absorption; ξ is the average logarithmic energy decrement during moderation; Σ_s is the macroscopic cross section of the medium scattering; $\xi \Sigma_s(1 \text{ eV})$ is the medium moderating capacity at 1 eV.

The fissile medium temperature coincides with the neutron gas temperature only in two cases: zero absorption and infinite moderating power of the medium. Nevertheless, this expression is quite convenient for obtaining average cross sections in the thermal region for thermal reactors.

The cross sections are averaged over the neutron spectrum according to the following expression:

$$\langle \sigma(E_g, T) \rangle = \frac{\int_0^{E_g} E^{1/2} e^{-E/(kT_{NG})} \sigma(E, T) dE}{\int_0^{E_g} E^{1/2} e^{-E/(kT_{NG})} dE}, \quad (2)$$

where σ is the nuclear reaction microsection; E is the neutron energy; E_{TP} is the limiting energy of thermal neutrons.

The result of averaging according to expression (2) for the capture, fission, and absorption microsections with the microsections σ dependences on the neutron velocity v_n of the $\sigma \propto 1/v_n$ type (or different from them) typical for exothermic nuclear reactions has a general form (here the expression for the fission reaction microsection σ_f is given):

$$\langle \sigma_f \rangle = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \sigma_f^T \cdot \sqrt{\frac{300}{T_{\text{NG}}}} \cdot g_f(T_{\text{NG}}) \cdot F(z_g), \quad (3)$$

where σ_f^T is the fission thermal microsection at a neutron velocity of 2200 m/s; T_{HT} is the neutron gas temperature calculated according to (1); $g_f(T_{\text{HT}})$ is the Westcott factor (Tables 1, 2) for the fission reaction [66-68]; $F(z_{\text{TP}})$ is the correction function; $z_{\text{TP}} = E_{\text{TP}}/(kT)$ is the dimensionless maximum energy for the Maxwell spectrum, i.e., the "crosslinking energy" of the Maxwell and Fermi neutron spectra.

For the microsections of other neutron nuclear reactions, e.g., radiative capture and absorption, expression (3) with the cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum has a similar form. The Westcott factor (Tables 1, 2 [68]) describes the difference between the microsections σ dependence on the neutron velocity v_n and the $\propto 1/v_n$ law and strongly depends on the medium temperature. The Westcott factor equals 1 if the corresponding reaction cross section exactly obeys the $\sim 1/v_n$ law.

The correction function $F(z)$ is obtained from the solution of the transcendental equation for crosslinking the Maxwell and Fermi spectra: $\Phi_M(E_{\text{TP}}) = \Phi_F(E_{\text{TP}})$. It is known that its argument z depends on the limiting "crosslinking energy" and approximately equals 5 for VVER and 6 for RBMK [66, 67]. The values of the function $F(z)$ are tabulated and available in reference books. It should be noted that the function values change with temperature, which affects the average cross sections.

Expressions (1) and (3) are used to calculate the temperature dependences of the nuclear fission and radiative capture reactions cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum for ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu , and the temperature dependences of the radiative capture cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum for ^{238}U .

When calculating the neutron gas temperatures according to expression (1), the fissile fuel medium temperature varied in the interval from 300 K to 2100 K

and the neutron absorption microsections varied in the thermal energies range from 0.025 eV to 0.181 eV; the neutron scattering microsections at an energy of 1 eV for the fissile fuel medium nuclides were taken from the nuclear database ENDF/B-VII.0. The upper limit of 2100 K for the investigated temperature range was determined by the Westcott factor values limited by that temperature of the neutron gas [68].

When calculating the temperatures of the neutron gas according to expression (1) as applied to thermal reactors with water as a moderator, the medium moderating capacity, i.e., the $\xi \Sigma_s$ term, is determined mainly by the hydrogen moderating capacity. The medium absorption macroscopic cross section contained in expression (1) as the numerator of the second term enclosed in brackets, is determined mainly by the absorption cross sections values in the thermal region for ^{238}U as a nuclide, which usually makes up more than 90 % of the nuclear fuel composition for thermal reactors. Therefore, for the values of $\xi \approx \xi_H = 1,0$, $\sigma_s \approx \sigma_s^H \approx 20,4$ barn, $\sigma_a^{238} = \sigma_c^{238} \approx 2,7$ barn, where ξ_H is the average logarithmic energy decrement for hydrogen and σ_c^{238} is the radiative neutron capture

reaction microsection for ^{238}U , the bracketed second term in expression (1) can practically be neglected, and the neutron gas temperature will practically coincide with the fissile medium temperature. If the nuclei heavier than hydrogen, e. g., carbon, oxygen, or ^{238}U itself, were considered as the main moderator, then the second term in the brackets in expression (1) could no longer be neglected, and the neutron gas temperatures would significantly exceed the fissile medium temperature. In calculations, e. g., for the uranium dioxide fuel or MOX fuel without a water moderator, the main moderator is oxygen, and the main absorber, as in the previous case, is ^{238}U . Then, since $\xi_O = 0,12$, $\sigma_s^O \approx 3,45$ barn, and $\sigma_a^{238} = \sigma_c^{238} \approx 2,7$ barn, the neutron gas temperature calculation according to expression (1) for the fissile medium temperatures in the interval from 300 K to 2100 K will give the temperatures values interval from 1200 K to 4600 K for the neutron gas. In this case, the application of the approach based on the relations (1) and (3) is impossible due to the lack of the Westcott factor tabular values for neutron gas temperatures exceeding 2100 K [68].

The calculated temperature dependences of the nuclear fission and radiative capture reactions cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum for ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu are shown in figures 1 and 2. In Fig. 2 the calculated temperature dependence of the radiative capture cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum for ^{238}U is shown as well.

Table 1.

Westcott factor for $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ fission and radiative capture reactions [68].

T, K	300	400	500	600	700	900	1100	1300	1500	1600	1800	1900	2100
g_f	1,058	1,150	1,305	1,518	1,768	2,290	2,746	3,091	3,328	3,412	3,521	3,552	3,572
g_c	1,154	1,374	1,713	2,159	2,672	3,724	4,630	5,314	5,782	5,947	6,164	6,226	6,269

Table 2.

Westcott factor for $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ fission and radiative capture reactions [68].

T, K	300	400	500	700	800	900	1000	1100	1200	1300	1400	1500	1700	2100
g_f	0,976	0,954	0,938	0,920	0,914	0,910	0,907	0,903	0,900	0,893	0,891	0,887	0,887	0,885
g_c	0,978	0,964	0,960	0,970	0,978	0,987	0,993	0,998	1,000	1,001	0,999	0,996	0,986	0,958

Table 3.

Nuclear reaction cross sections for thermal neutron energies [66, 69].

Nuclide	V_{T*}	σ_f^T, b	σ_c^T, b	$\alpha^T = \sigma_c / \sigma_f$	I_c, b	I_f, b
U-235	2.42	580	107	0.184	142	277
U-238		0	2.7	0	277	0
Pu-239	2.88	750	315	---	188	312

As is seen from Fig. 1, in the studied temperature interval there is a fundamental difference in the temperature dependences of the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ nuclear fission reactions cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum. The averaged cross section of the $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ fission increases with the temperature increase and reaches a maximum at 1500 K, and then de-

creases with the temperature increase, i.e., the dependence has a resonant form. The averaged cross section of the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ fission gradually decreases with the temperature increase. Similar temperature dependences of the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ nuclear fission reactions cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum are also obtained in [69].

Fig. 1. Dependence on the fissile fuel medium temperature for the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ fission cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum (the cross sections values are normalized to σ_f^T (fission thermal microsection) and given in Table 3).

Fig. 2. Dependence on the fissile fuel medium temperature for the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$, $^{238}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ radiative capture cross sections averaged over the thermal neutrons spectrum (the cross sections values are normalized to the thermal microsection σ_c^T of the neutron radiative capture with their values given in Table 3).

Dependences in Fig. 2 show a significant increase of the $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ radiative capture cross section with the temperature increase and a slight increase of the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{238}_{92}\text{U}$ radiative capture cross section.

2.2. Dependences on the reactor fuel temperature for the cross sections averaged over the total neutron spectrum.

As already noted, the calculation of the cross sections averaged over the thermalized part of the spectrum using expression (3), which includes the tabular values of the Westcott factor, is possible for thermal reactors with a water moderator and with moderators consisting of nuclei with small atomic numbers, and therefore having a high moderating ability. However, if heavier nuclei, such as carbon and oxygen, serve as the main moderator, problems already arise with calculations according to (3) due to the lack of tabular values of the Westcott factor at neutron gas temperatures above 2100 K.

To calculate the dependences on the fissile medium temperature for the cross sections averaged over the neutron spectrum, an approach has been developed that does not rely on the Westcott factor values use. This approach, in contrast to the one presented above, is developed not only for thermal reactors, and therefore allows to calculate the cross sections averaged over the total neutron spectrum (for neutron energy range from thermal to 10 MeV). Its main provisions are published in [41, 42, 43, 47-51].

As is known, the influence of the medium nuclei thermal motion is reduced to the resonances width increase and the resonances height decrease. This effect, by analogy with optics, is usually called the Doppler effect [66]. Since in the low energies range the resonance levels are observed only for heavy nuclei, the Doppler effect is noticeable only during the neutrons interaction with such nuclei and is stronger, the higher the medium temperature.

In the Microsoft Fortran Power Station 4.0 (MFPS 4.0) software environment a computer program has been developed that allows calculating the resonant neutron reactions cross sections dependences on the neutron energy with an allowance for the Doppler effect. In the calculations, the neutron reactions cross sections dependences on the reactor nuclides neutron energy taken from the ENDF/B-VII.0 database and corresponding to an ambient temperature of 300 K were used as input data. For instance, in Fig. 3 the result of calculating the radiative neutron captures cross sections dependences on the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ energy (in the lower energy range) at the various fissile medium temperatures in the range from 300 K to 3000 K are shown.

Using this program, the dependences of the scattering, fission, and radiative neutron capture reactions cross sections for the main reactor fuel nuclides $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$, $^{238}_{92}\text{U}$, $^{239}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ at various temperatures in the range from 300 K to 3000 K are obtained.

A program has also been developed and used for obtaining the calculated dependences of the cross sections $\bar{\sigma}_j^i(\bar{r}, T, t)$ averaged over the neutron spectrum for the main reactor nuclides and the main reactor nuclear neutron reactions at the indicated temperatures. Here the neutron spectrum was specified in a combined form as follows: in the form of a Maxwell spectrum $\Phi_1(E_n)$ for energies below the limiting thermalization energy E_{tp}^{tepM} ; in the form of the Fermi spectrum $\Phi_\Phi(E_n)$ for the moderating and absorbing medium if energies were above E_{tp}^{tepM} , but below E_f (E_f was the upper energy of the Fermi spectrum neutrons); as the fission spectrum for $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ if energies were above E_f , but below E_n^{max} [70, 71]. The neutron gas temperature for the Maxwell distribution was

specified by a relation like the expression (1), but somewhat modified based on the approach given in [66]. According to this approach, formally, the shortcomings of the standard moderation theory in the sphere of thermalization can be partially reduced if, instead of the average logarithmic energy loss $\bar{\xi}$ of the standard theory (which does not depend on the neutron energy and, as

is known, is used for a medium of nuclei with atomic numbers exceeding 10 $\bar{\xi} \approx 2/A$), the variable $\xi(z) = \xi\varphi(z)$, where $\varphi(z) = (1 - 2/z)$ and $z = E_n/kT$, should be introduced.

Fig. 3. Calculated dependences of the $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ neutron radiative capture reaction cross sections on $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ energy at the various temperatures in the range from 300 K to 3000 K.

So, within the framework of the considered formalism, the neutron gas temperature was specified by the following expression:

$$T_n = T \left[1 + 1,8 \frac{\Sigma_a(kT)}{\bar{\xi}\Sigma_s} \right], \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\xi}$ was the averaged logarithmic energy decrement during moderation over the entire Maxwellian spectrum energy range $\xi(z)$ at $kT=1$ eV.

In Fig. 4 the calculated temperature dependences of cross sections $\bar{\sigma}_j^i(\vec{r}, T)$ averaged over the neutron spectrum for the main reactor nuclides $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$, $^{238}_{92}\text{U}$

and $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ for the main reactor nuclear neutron reactions are shown.

As is seen, the calculated dependences on the fissile medium temperature in the range from 300 K to 6000 K for the cross sections averaged over the combined Maxwell and Fermi spectrum can behave as follows:

- first grow and then fall with the temperature increase, i.e., have a resonant character (e. g., for $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$);
- both grow with the fissile medium temperature increasing (e. g., for $^{238}_{92}\text{U}$) and fall (e. g., for $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$).

Fig. 4. Dependences on the fissile medium temperature at various values of the Fermi and Maxwell spectra limiting energy for the $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$, $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{238}_{92}\text{U}$ fission cross sections (a) and radiative capture cross sections (b) averaged over the combined Maxwell and Fermi spectrum.

This can be explained by the fact that for $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ the resonant region begins at much lower energies than for $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ (Fig. 5 [72]), and with the fuel temperature increase the neutron gas temperature also increases and causes a shift of the Maxwellian neutron distribution

maximum towards higher neutrons energies, i.e., the neutron gas spectrum hardening, at which the number of neutrons falling into the $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ resonant region increases, which just makes the averaged cross sections

to grow. For $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ this process is not so significant because its resonant region is located higher in energies, and the neutron gas spectrum hardening associated with the fuel temperature increase (in the considered range) does not cause a significant increase in the number of neutrons falling into the resonant region. Note that, as is seen from the same Fig. 7, for uranium 235, the resonance, which can cause the dependence of the fission cross section averaged over the thermal spectrum like for plutonium 239, is located much higher than for plutonium 239, approximately at about 1 eV.

Fig. 5. Nuclides fission cross sections for uranium 235 (curve 1), uranium 238 (curve 2) and plutonium 239 (curve 3) depending on neutron energies [72].

2.3. Dependences on the reactor fuel temperature for the MOX fuel and uranium dioxide fuel heat source densities.

The heat source density of the MOX fuel (a mixture of ^{238}U dioxide and ^{239}Pu dioxide) in a thermal reactor with water as a moderator, e. g., BWR, was calculated according to the expression:

$$S(T) = Q_{\text{Pu}} \cdot \Phi \cdot \langle \sigma_f^{\text{Pu}}(T) \rangle \cdot N^{\text{Pu}}, \quad (5)$$

where $Q_{\text{Pu}} = 210.3$ MeV was the thermal energy of one ^{239}Pu nucleus fission; $\Phi = 10^{13}$ $1/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ s})$ was the neutron flux density; $\langle \sigma_f^{\text{Pu}} \rangle$ was the fission cross section averaged over the ^{239}Pu thermal spectrum (see expression (3)); N^{Pu} was the plutonium nuclei concentration.

In calculations, the MOX fuel density value was assumed 10.82 g/cm^3 .

The heat source density for uranium dioxide fuel (a mixture of ^{235}U dioxide and ^{238}U dioxide) in a thermal reactor with water as a moderator was also calculated according to an expression similar to (5), at

The ^{238}U data presented in Fig. 4 (due to the high fission threshold exceeding 1 MeV, the averaged cross section of the ^{238}U fission is practically insensitive to the neutron spectrum hardening caused by the fuel temperature increase) confirm the temperature dependence of the radiative capture cross section, since its resonant region is located as low as the ^{239}Pu resonant region.

$Q_{235} = 203.0$ MeV and the uranium dioxide fuel density of 10.82 g/cm^3 .

It was assumed that the neutron flux density Φ should remain constant with the fissile medium temperature increase, since the main neutron absorption was associated with ^{238}U , and its radiative capture cross section averaged over the thermal spectrum should increase insignificantly with the medium temperature increase in the studied range (Fig. 2, Table 2).

An analysis of the heat source density dependences on the fissile medium temperature obtained for MOX fuel (Fig. 6) shows that with a temperature increase from 300 K to 1500 K the source density nonlinear increase by 45 % at 300 K is observed. With a further temperature increase to 2100 K, some density decrease is observed. But an analysis of the heat source densities dependences on the fissile medium temperature obtained for uranium dioxide fuel (Fig. 7) shows that with the temperature increase from 300 K to 2100 K, a nonlinear decrease in the heat source density is observed. Such behavior of the heat source densities is explained by the obtained temperature dependences of the ^{239}Pu fission cross section and the ^{235}U fission cross section averaged over the thermal spectrum (Fig. 1).

Fig. 6. The heat source densities dependences on the temperature of the fuel fissile medium of the ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu dioxides mixture for three compositions (^{239}Pu enrichment of 1 %, 5 %, 10 %).

Fig. 7. The heat source density dependences on the ^{238}U and ^{235}U dioxides fuel mixture temperature for three compositions (^{235}U enrichment of 10 %, 5 % and 1 %).

3. Experiment: the temperature dependences obtained for heat source densities and the dynamics features of the accident at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant Unit 3.

Thus, a fundamental difference in the temperature dependences of the heat sources densities for MOX fuel and uranium oxide fuel has been discovered and explained for the studied interval of temperatures. Moreover, the obtained temperature dependences of the heat source densities for the fissile fuel medium presented in Figs. 6 and 7 allow to identify some features of the accident at the Fukushima Daiichi Unit 3

As is known, one third of the nuclear fuel load at this Unit was MOX fuel, the rest of the fuel was uranium dioxide one. The accident developed as follows. When trying to cool the overheated nuclear reactor by pumping cold sea water through it, due to the water decomposition an uncontrolled formation of hydrogen gas occurred, which led to an explosive mixture formation and explosion, which caused the nuclear reactor destruction. The thermal water decomposition temperature is quite high, 3800 K. Therefore, most likely, the hydrogen formation occurred not as a result of thermal hydrolysis of water, but at a lower temperature as a result of the steam-zirconium reaction [82-85], i.e., the

exothermic reaction of the interaction of fuel elements zirconium cladding and water with the zirconium dioxide formation and the gaseous hydrogen release ($\text{Zr} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{ZrO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2 + Q$, where $Q=6530$ kJ/kg was the released heat).

The steam-zirconium reaction has several features as follows: it starts at approximately 1173 K – 1223 K, develops very quickly, and at 1473 K (as the released heat additionally heats the zirconium, an autocatalysis develops) becomes self-sustaining.

Since the hydrogen explosion at the reactor occurred after the restoration of the cooling water supply to the reactor, it could be concluded that due to the long-term disruption of the heat removal system caused by the tsunami impact, the superheated reactor fuel temperature reached the values of the steam-zirconium reaction beginning in the interval from 1173 K to 1223 K. The heat source density dependence on the fuel temperature obtained for the MOX fuel (Fig. 6) showed that in that case the heat source density of the Unit 3 MOX fuel should increase, reaching a maximum at 1500 K. Such behavior of the heat source density of the MOX fuel could cause the further MOX fuel heating to a temperature of 1473 K, at which the steam-zirconium reaction of the hydrogen gas formation would begin to

develop very quickly and would become the self-sustaining one. It should be emphasized that according to the heat source density dependence on the fuel temperature obtained for the uranium dioxide fuel (Fig. 7), there would not be any very rapid formation of hydrogen for the uranium dioxide fuel.

Therefore, the difference in the temperature dependences of the heat source densities for MOX fuel and uranium oxide fuel could cause a more intense hydrogen release, and, consequently, a more powerful hydrogen explosion of Unit 3 compared to the case when its total fuel load would be the ordinary uranium dioxide fuel. This conclusion coincides with information reports about a more powerful hydrogen explosion at Unit 3 compared to the hydrogen explosion at the Fukushima Daiichi NPP Unit 1, where there was no MOX fuel loading.

Further fuel heating to the oxide fuel melting point 2800 K could be explained by the water pumping system destruction during a hydrogen explosion, and hence by the long-term absence of heat removal necessary to prevent fuel melting. This is also possible with the same dependences of the heat source densities for MOX fuel (Fig. 6), although, as already noted, there is some decrease of the heat source density when the temperature rises from 1500 K to 2100 K, and, apparently, even at the thermal sources densities dependences of the uranium dioxide fuel (Fig. 7). For eliminating all the above assumptions as to the fuel temperature change, it is necessary to look for the solutions of the heat transfer equation with the heat source densities obtained for given initial and boundary conditions. Now it is not possible to do this just because of the lack of information about the initial and boundary conditions and their possible changes during the accident development at the Fukushima Daiichi NPP.

However, to explain the possible kinetics features of the fuel heating to a melting temperature of 2800 K associated with the discovered temperature features of the MOX fuel (Fig. 6), and the ^{239}Pu cross sections averaged over the neutron spectrum (Fig. 4), the following considerations seem to be of interest.

As a result of the steam-zirconium reaction, especially after a hydrogen explosion that disrupted the system of water supply to the reactor, the water amount in the reactor decreases, which causes its moderating ability decreasing and the neutron spectrum hardening, i.e., the maximum of the Maxwellian distribution of thermalized neutrons shifts towards higher energies. For a harder neutron spectrum, the temperature dependence of the ^{239}Pu fission cross sections averaged over the thermal neutron spectrum shown in Fig. 1 and used for calculating the temperature dependence of the MOX fuel heat source density (Fig. 6) should be replaced by the temperature dependence of the $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ fission cross sections averaged over the neutron spectrum for $E = 3kT$ (Fig. 4). Since this temperature dependence of

$^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ fission cross sections averaged over the neutron spectrum demonstrates a nonlinear growth with a maximum at a temperature of 3000 K, the temperature

dependence of the heat source density for the MOX fuel, which is calculated according to expression (5), should behave in the same way. In other words, in contrast to the dependence in Fig. 6, in this case the temperature dependence of the heat source density for the MOX fuel with a maximum at 3000 K is obtained. Thus, due to such a heat source density temperature dependence, a smooth, non-linear increase of the MOX fuel temperature can occur from the steam-zirconium reaction beginning temperature of 1173 K...1223 K, through its autocatalysis temperature of 1473 K to the fuel melting temperature of 2800 K. Consequently, first the MOX fuel in the Fukushima Daiichi NPP Unit 3 should have melted and contributed to the reactor uranium dioxide fuel melting.

The periodic (pulsating) emergency increase of the temperature and pressure in the Unit 3 destroyed reactor during the reactor cooling, the cause of which was previously unknown, can also be explained by the non-linear temperature dependence of the heat source density for MOX fuel obtained in a resonant form (Fig. 6).

The revealed features of the MOX fuel temperature behavior and their supposed influence on the accident kinetics in the Unit 3 could be eliminated by excluding the thermalized tail (the Maxwellian part of the spectrum) from the energy spectrum of neutrons being moderated. To do this, at the first stage of an overheated reactor cooling, it would be necessary to technically implement the replacement of a water moderator-coolant with a moderator-coolant having a mass number significantly greater than the mass number of hydrogen, e. g., nitrogen, carbon monoxide, liquid metal tin, lead, mercury, bismuth or a bismuth-lead mixture, which would lead to the neutron spectrum hardening and would also allow to avoid the hydrogen explosions.

It should be especially noted, as noted above in the introduction to this paper, that the authors' theoretical model of the accident dynamics, which, in their opinion, explains well the known experimental data on the accident dynamics, is based on the dynamics of nuclear reactions involving neutrons. But where did neutrons come from? The authors try to find an answer to this difficult question, since according to information reports, the nuclear power plant reactors were "shut down" after having received a message about a tsunami and there should not seem to be any neutrons.

Several events scenarios are possible here.

It can be assumed that the operator, having received a message about the tsunami and not assuming that something extraordinary might happen, i.e., that the protective breakwater would not be able to prevent the wave hitting, did not execute an emergency shut down of the reactor, but launched the usual procedure for automatically bringing the reactor to minimum power, which is usually carried out before any preventive works. Note that the procedure itself for the reactor power reduction from the operating level is carried out via a gradual power decrease by small amounts and therefore takes a rather long time.

It is also known that after the reactor is "shut down", in the reactor core for a long time (about 1 hour, there is even a corresponding term in the formula for

the correct calculation of the reactor residual heat release, taking into account the delayed neutrons contribution), there is enough of delayed neutrons emitted by accumulated fission fragments. Indeed, the epicenter of the earthquake that occurred on March 11, 2011 and generated a tsunami was located at a 180 km distance from the coast, where the Fukushima Daiichi NPP industrial site was located [68]. Tsunami speed was 200 m/s. Consequently, it reached the nuclear power plant in 15 minutes after the reactor was "shut down".

It is also possible that after the reactor was subject to emergency "shut down", due to the MOX fuel temperature features described in detail above the fuel melted and accidentally formed its supercritical mass, which created a neutron flux during the fission chain reaction development.

It is also known that after the reactor is "shut down" in the reactor core for a long time (about 1 hour, there is even a corresponding term in the formula for the correct calculation of the reactor's residual heat release, taking into account the contribution of delayed neutrons) a sufficient number of delayed neutrons emitted by the accumulated fission fragments. Indeed, the epicenter of the earthquake that occurred on March 11, 2011, and generated the tsunami was 180 km away from the coast where the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear power plant site is located, for example [86]. I VICTUED A tsunami velocity of 200 m/c. Consequently, the tsunami reached the nuclear power plant 15 minutes after the reactor was "shut down".

Thus, at the time of the tsunami strike, there could be enough neutrons in the NPP nuclear reactors to start all neutron-nuclear processes mentioned above.

Moreover, based on the current state of the fuel, which continues to heat up during four years after the accident and therefore requires continuous pumping of thousand tons of water through the destroyed reactors to cool them, as well as on the reports about the periodic pulsations of the pumped water temperature, it can be assumed that it is the neutron-nuclear processes, such as wave burning, temperature blow-up modes, and the dynamics of dissipative structures of radiation-induced defects, that are responsible for these processes.

In conclusion, the authors of the article express their gratitude to all of their colleagues V. D. Rusov, A. A. Kakaev, E. V. Grehan, S. I. Kosenko, O. I. Pantak, who in their works have laid the basic foundation for the development of further research into the very important features of the great accident at unit 3 of the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear power plant.

Conclusions.

A fundamental difference in the temperature dependences of the fission cross sections averaged over the neutron thermal spectrum for $^{235}_{92}\text{U}$ and $^{239}_{94}\text{Pu}$ is found and explained.

The heat source densities temperature dependences for the thermal reactors MOX and UO_2 fuels are calculated.

The MOX fuel temperature behavior features discovered during the research made it possible to explain

some dynamics features of the accident at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant Unit 3.

It is necessary to note in conclusion that so far, no data have been published on neutrons either during the accident at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant, or after it and even up to the present day, although a remote antineutrino technology for monitoring the reactor fuel nuclide composition has already been developed, e. g. [38, 78], which can also be used to obtain data on neutrons.

References

1. Feinberg, S.M., & Kunegin, V.V. (1958). Discussion Content. In: Record of Proceeding Session B-10, UN Int.Conf. on the Peaceful Uses for Atomic Energy (vol. 9 (2), p.447). Geneva, Switzerland.
2. Feoktistov, L.P. (1989). Neutron fission wave. In: Reports of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR (vol. 309 (4), pp. 864-867).
3. Feoktistov, L.P. (1993). Safety is key to the renaissance of nuclear power. In Advances in the physical sciences (vol. 163 (8), pp. 89-102).
4. Teller, E., Ishikawa, M., & Wood, L. (1995). Completely automated nuclear reactors for long-term operation. In: Proc. "Frontiers in Physical Symposium" Joint American Physical Society and American Association of Physics Teachers Texas Meeting, Lubbock, Texas, (1995): Preprint UCRL-JC-122708; Teller E., Ishikawa M., Wood L., et al., in: Proc. Int. Conf. on Emerging Nuclear Energy System (ICENEC'96), Obninsk, Russia (1996), p. 123 (Retrieved from http://www-phys.llnl.gov/adv_energy_src/ICENES96.html); Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Preprint No. UCRL-JC-122708-RT2.
5. Goldin, V.Ya., & Anistratov, D.Yu. (1995). Fast neutron reactor in a self-regulating neutron-nuclear mode. Math modeling, 7 (10), 21-32.
6. Goldin, V.Ya., Sosnin, N.V., & Troshchiev, Yu.V. (1998). Fast neutron reactor in self-regulating mode of the 2nd kind. In: Reports of the Academy of Sciences, Mathematical physics, (vol. 358 (6), pp.747-748).
7. Seifritz, W. (1998). On the burn-up theory of fast soliton reactors. Int. J. Hydrogen Energy, 23, 77-82.
8. Van Dam, H. (2000). Self-stabilizing criticality waves. In: Annals of Nuclear Energy, (vol. 27, pp. 1505-1521).
9. Sekimoto, H., & Ryu, K. (2000). A New Reactor Burnup Concept "CANDLE". PHYSOR 2000, Pittsburgh, May 7-11, 2000.
10. Sekimoto, H., & Ryu, K. (2000). Feasibility Study on the CANDLE New Burnup Strategy. Trans. American Nuclear Society, 82, 207-208.
11. Sekimoto, H., & Ryu, K. (2000). A Long Life Lead-Bismuth Cooled Reactor with CANDLE Burnup. ICENES 2000, Petten, The Netherlands, Sept. 24-28, 2000.
12. Sekimoto, H. (2000). Long Life Reactor with "CANDLE" Burnup Strategy. 4th Japan-Korea Seminar on Advanced Reactors, Tokyo, Japan, October 19-20, 2000.

13. Sekimoto, H., & Ryu, K. (2000). Demonstrating the Feasibility of the CANDLE Burnup Scheme for Fast Reactors. *Trans. American Nuclear Society*, 83, 45.
14. Akhiezer, A.I., Khizhnyak, N.A., Shulga, N.F., Pilipenko, V.V., & Davydov L.N. (2001). Slow nuclear burning. *Problems of atomic science and technology*, 6, 272-275.
15. Khizhnyak, N.A. (2001). On the theory of the initial stage of slow nuclear burning. *Problems of atomic science and technology*, 6, 279-282.
16. Sekimoto, H., Ryu, K., & Yoshimura, Y. (2001). CANDLE: The New Burnup Strategy. *Nuclear science and engineering*, 139, 306-317.
17. Sekimoto, H., Toshinsky, V., & Ryu, K. (2001). Natural Uranium Utilization without Enrichment and Reprocessing. GLOBAL-2001, Paris, France, September 9-13, 2001.
18. Sekimoto, H. (2001). Applications of "CANDLE" Burnup Strategy to Several Reactors. ARWIF-2001, Chester, UK, October 22-24, 2001.
19. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Kosenko, S.I., & Bolshakov, V.N. (2003). Accounting for delayed neutrons in non-stationary neutron multiplier systems and kinetic equations of the L.P. Feoktistov reactor. *International Conference on High Energy Density Physics "VII Zababakhin Scientific Readings"*, Snezhinsk, Russia, February 21-24, 2003. RFNC-VNIITF Publishing House.
20. Rusov, V., Tarasov, V., Kosenko, S., & Bolshakov, V. (2003). Accounting for delayed neutrons in non-stationary neutron multiplier systems and kinetic equations of the L.P. Feoktistov reactor. *International Conference of Young Scientists on Theoretical and Experimental Physics "Evrika-2003"*, Lviv, May 21-23. Lviv National University
21. Rusov, V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Vaschenko V.N., Tarasov V.A. et al. (2003). Antineutrino spectrum of the Earth and the problem of oscillating geantineutrino deficit. Retrieved from hep-ph/0312296.
22. Rusov, V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Vaschenko V.N., Tarasov V.A. et al. (2004). Geantineutrino Spectrum and Slow Nuclear Burning on the Boundary of the Liquid and Solid Phases of the Earth's core. Retrieved from hep-ph/0402039.
23. Rusov V.D., Tarasov V.A., Litvinov D.A., Bolshakov V.N., Saranyuk D.N. (2004). R-process of the heavy nuclei creation in the neutron flow formed via slow wave of the nuclear burning at the boundary between liquid and solid phases of the planetary core. *The Gamow Memorial International Conference dedicated to 100-th anniversary of George Gamov "ASTROPHYSICS AND COSMOLOGY AFTER GAMOW - THEORY AND OBSERVATIONS"* (Odesa, Ukraine, August 8-14, 2004).
24. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Kosenko, S.I., Litvinov, D.A., & Bolshakov, V.N. (2004). Accounting for delayed neutrons in non-stationary neutron multiplier systems and kinetic equations of the L.P. Feoktistov reactor. *The XVI International Conference on the Physics of Radiation Phenomena and Radiation Materials Science, New Nuclear Power Reactors and Irradiation Technology*. Kharkiv: NSC KIPT.
25. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Kosenko, S.I., & Bolshakov, V.N. (2005). Modeling of L.P. Feoktistov fast reactor kinetics. *The International Conference on High Energy Density Physics "VIII Zababakhin Scientific Readings"*, Snezhinsk, Russia, September 5-10, 2005. RFNC-VNIITF Publishing House.
26. Chen, X-N., & Werner, M. (2005). Transverse buckling effects on solitary burn-up waves. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 47, 1301-1313.
27. Rusov, V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Vaschenko V.N., Tarasov V.A., et al. (2006). Geantineutrino Spectrum, ${}^3\text{He}/{}^4\text{He}$ -ratio radial distribution and Slow Nuclear Burning on the Boundary of the Liquid and Solid Phases of the Earth's core. Retrieved from nucl-th/0605025.
28. Rusov, V., Tarasov, V., Kosenko, S., & Bolshakov, V. (2006). Accounting for delayed neutrons in non-stationary neutron multiplier systems and kinetic equations of the L.P. Feoktistov reactor. *Bulletin of Lviv University: Physical series*, 39, 261-267.
29. Rusov, V.D., Pavlovich, V.N., Vashchenko, V.N., Tarasov, V.A. et al. (2006). Spectrum of geoneutrinos and slow nuclear combustion at the boundary of the liquid and solid phases of the Earth's core. *The IV conference on high energy physics, nuclear physics and accelerators.*, Kharkiv, Ukraine, February 27-March 3. NSC KIPT.
30. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Kosenko, S.I., & Bolshakov, V.N. (2006). 3D modeling of fast reactor kinetics L.P. Feoktistov. *The IV conference on high energy physics, nuclear physics and accelerators*, Kharkiv, Ukraine, February 27-March 3. NSC KIPT.
31. Rusov V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Vaschenko V.N., Tarasov V.A. et al. Geantineutrino spectrum and slow nuclear burning on the boundary of the liquid and solid phases of the earth's core. *Int. Conf. Current Problems in Nuclear Physics and Atomic Energy (NPAE-Kyiv2006)*, Kyiv, Ukraine, May 29-June 03.
32. Rusov V.D., Tarasov V.A., Kosenko S.I., Bolshakov V.N. (2006). 3-D modeling of kinetics of L.P. Feoktistov fast reactor. *Int. Conf. Current Problems in Nuclear Physics and Atomic Energy (NPAE-Kyiv2006)*, Kyiv, Ukraine, May 29-June 03.
33. Rusov V.D., Tarasov V.A., Skalozubov V.I., Bolshakov V.N. et al. (2006). 3-D simulation of the Feoktistov fast reactor kinetics. *The 2nd International Conference on Quantum Electrodynamics and Statistical Physics (QEDSP2006)*, Kharkiv, Ukraine, September 19-23.
34. Rusov V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Vaschenko V.N., Tarasov V.A. et al. (2006). About possibility of the slow nuclear burning on the boundary of the liquid and solid phases of Earth's core and geoneutrino spectrum. *The 2nd International Conference on Quantum Electrodynamics and Statistical Physics (QEDSP2006)*, Kharkiv, Ukraine, September 19-23.
35. Rusov V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Vaschenko V.N., Tarasov V.A et al. (2006). Geantineutrino spectrum, ${}^3\text{He}/{}^4\text{He}$ -ratio distribution in the earth's interior and slow nuclear burning on the boundary of the liquid and solid phases of the earth's core. *Ukrainian Antarctic journal*, 4-5, 182-202.

36. Rusov V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Tarasov V.A., Sharf, I.V., & Bolshakov, V.N. (2007). Soliton-like waves of nuclear combustion in neutron-multiplicating media. Theory and computational experiment. The V conference on high energy physics, nuclear physics and accelerators, Kharkov, Ukraine. February 26-March 2. NSC KIPT.
37. Rusov V.D., Pavlovich V.N., Vaschenko V.N., Tarasov V.A. et al. (2007). Geoantineutrino spectrum and slow nuclear burning on the boundary of the liquid and solid phases of the Earth's core. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, vol. 112, B09203, 1-16. DOI: 10.1029/2005JB004212.
38. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., & Litvinov, D.A. (2008). *Physics of reactor antineutrinos*. Moscow: URSS.
39. Weaver, K.D., Gilleland, J.R., Ahlfeld, C.E., Whitmer, C., & Zimmerman, G.B. (2010). A Once-Through Fuel Cycle for Fast Reactors. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, April, 132, 1-6.
40. Ellis, T., Petroski, R., Hejzlar, P., Zimmerman, G. et al. (2010). Traveling-wave Reactors: A Truly Sustainable and Full-Scale Resource for Global Energy Needs. The 2010 International Congress on Advances in Nuclear Power Plants (ICAPP 2010), San Diego, CA, USA, Paper No. 10189.
41. Rusov, V.D., Linnik, E.P., Tarasov, V.A. et al. (2011). Traveling wave reactor and condition of existence of nuclear burning soliton-like wave in neutron-multiplicating media. *Energies*, 4, 1337–1361; doi: 10.3390/en4091337.
42. Rusov, V.D., Litvinov, D.A., Linnik, E.P., Vaschenko, V.M., Zelentsova, T.N., Beglaryan, M.E....Kavatsky, P.E. (2013). KamLand-Experiment and Soliton-Like Nuclear Georeactor. Part 1. Comparison of the Theory with Experiment. *Journal of Modern Physics*, 4, 528-550.
43. Tarasov, V.A., Rusov, V.D., & Vaschenko, V.M. (2013). Nuclear power reactor and method for operating the reactor. 2nd Life Nuclear Solutions GmbH (Patent Application), HOEFER&PARTNER, Jun. 25, 2013, SLN130601PCT-6/KL, P. 1-18.
44. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., & Vaschenko, V.N. (2013). Traveling wave nuclear reactor. Kyiv: Publishing group A.C.C.
45. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Sharf, I.V., Vaschenko, V.M., Linnik E.P., Zelentsova T.N....Grechan, E.V. (2015). On some fundamental peculiarities of the traveling wave reactor operation. In: *Science and Technology of Nuclear Installations* (vol. 2015, pp. 1-23). Retrieved from arXiv:1207.3695v1 [nucl-th].
46. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Eingorn, M.V., Chernenko, S.A., & Kakaev, A.A. (2015). Ultra-slow wave nuclear burning of uranium-plutonium fissile medium on epithermal neutrons. *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, 83, 105-122. Retrieved from arXiv:1409.7343v2 [nucl-th].
47. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Chernenko, S.A., & Borikov, T.L. (2010). Modes with aggravation in the uranium-plutonium fissile medium. In: XII Kharkov thematic scientific readings; Problems of physics of high energy densities. Reports (pp. 94-102). Sarov, Russia: RFNC-VNIIEF Publishing House.
48. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., & Chernenko, S.A. (2011). Blow-up modes in the uranium-plutonium fissile medium of technical nuclear reactors and georeactors. *Questions of atomic science of technology. Series Physics of Radiation Damage and Radiation Materials Science*, 2(97), 112-121.
49. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Vaschenko, V.M., Linnik, E.P., Zelentsova, T.N., Beglaryan, M.E.... Grechan, E.V. (2013). Fukushima plutonium effect and blow-up regimes in neutron-multiplying media. *World Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, 3, 9-18. Retrieved from arXiv:1209.0648v1 [nucl-th].
50. Tarasov, V.A., Borikov, T.L., Kryzhanovskaia, T.V., Chernenko, S.A., & Rusov, V.D. (2007). Theory of dissipative structures of a kinetic system for defects of nonlinear physical system "metal + load + irradiation". Part 1,2 Questions of atomic science of technology. *Series Physics of Radiation Damage and Radiation Materials Science*, 2(90), 63-75.
51. Tarasov, V.A., Borikov, T.L., Kryzhanovskaia, T.V., Chernenko, S.A., & Rusov, V.D. (2007). Theory of dissipative structures of a kinetic system for defects of nonlinear physical system "metal + load + irradiation". Part 3-4 // Questions of atomic science of technology. *Series Physics of Radiation Damage and Radiation Materials Science*, 6(91), 18-35.
52. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Chernenko, S.A., Kakaev, A.A., Grechan, E.V., Kosenko, S.I., & Pantak, O.I. (2012). The temperature dependences distinction of thermal source densities of MOX-fuel and dioxide-fuel and related with it features of the Fukushima-1 NPP unit 3 accident. *Int. Conf. Current Problems in Nuclear Physics and Atomic Energy (NPAE-Kyiv2012)*, Kiv, Ukraine, September 10–14.
53. Rusov, V.D., Tarasov, V.A., Chernenko, S.A., Kakaev, A.A., Grechan, E.V., Kosenko, S.I., & Pantak, O.I. (2012). The temperature dependences distinction of thermal source densities of MOX-fuel and dioxide-fuel and related with it features of the Fukushima-1 NPP unit 3 accident. *The Third International Scientific and Technical Conference "Improving the Safety and Efficiency of Nuclear Energy"*, Odesa, Ukraine, September 24 – 28.
54. Fukushima Plutonium Effect: Melting MOX fuel may lead to neutron flux blow-up — 'Surprisingly' there's absolutely no reference data in any scientific literature (2014, January 6). *ENE NEWS (ENERGY NEWS)*. Retrieved from <http://enews.com/study-fukushima-plutonium-effect-melting-mox-fuel-lead-neutron-flux-blow-surprisingly-absolutely-data-scientific-literature-refer>
55. Moret, L. (2014, June 1). FUKUSHIMA: IMPACT OF FALLOUT ON OCEANS". In: Leuren Moret. *Global Nuclear Coverup*. Retrieved from <http://www.leurenmoret.info/currents/fukushima-impact-of-fallout.html>

56. Photo courtesy of TEPCO (2011, March 23). In: Fukushima Daiichi Reactor Number 3 and 4 Damage Analyses. Retrieved from <http://bigdustup.blogspot.com/2011/03/fukushima-daiichi-reactor-number-3-and.html>
57. Reactor Designer: It was a nuclear explosion” at Fukushima Unit 3; Plutonium scattered after blast — ABC: There’s willful denial and lying going on here, even at the highest levels (2013, November 5) ENE NEWS (ENERGY NEWS). Retrieved from <http://ene-news.com/reactor-designer-it-was-a-nuclear-explosion-at-fukushima-unit-3-plutonium-was-scattered-after-blast-abc-theres-willful-denial-and-lying-going-on-here-even-at-the-highest-levels>
58. S. Fujiwara & SPA magazine. Japanese Engineer: "There Was a Nuclear Explosion in Reactor 3 in Addition to a Hydrogen Explosion". (December 12, 2011). Retrieved from <http://ex-skf.blogspot.com/2011/12/japanese-engineer-there-was-nuclear.html>
59. Study: Evidence of “uncontrollable nuclear reaction” at Fukushima after 3/11 — “Emerging criticality” supported by data (PHOTOS). (2013, December 5). ENE NEWS (ENERGY NEWS). Retrieved from <http://enenews.com/study-evidence-of-uncontrollable-nuclear-reaction-after-fukushima-reactors-shutdown-emerged-criticality-supported-by-data-photos>
60. Pakhomov, S.A., & Dubasov, Yu.V. (2013). Estimation of Nuclear-Energy Excursion Possibility during Fukushima Daiichi NPP Accident. CTBTO: Science and Technology 2013 conference, Vienna, Austria, June 17-21. Retrieved from <http://www.ctbto.org/fileadmin/snt2013/posters/T2-P22.pdf>
61. Priyadarshi, A., Dominguez, G., & Thiemens, M.H. (2011). Evidence of neutron leakage at the Fukushima nuclear plant from measurements of radioactive ^{35S} in California. PNAS, 108(35), 14422–14425. Retrieved from www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.1109449108.
62. TEPCO: Fukushima nuclear Unit 1 did melt down in 2011 accident. (2015). Power Engineering.
63. Borozdin, K.N., Hogan, G.E., Morris, C., Priedhorsky, W.C., Saunders, Schultz, L.J., & Teasdale, M.E. (2003). Radiographic imaging with cosmic-ray muons. Nature, 422, 227. Retrieved from www.nature.com/nature
64. Borozdin, K., Greene, S., Lukic’, Z., Milner, E., Miyadera, H., Morris, C., & Perry, J. (2012, 12 October). Cosmic Ray Radiography of the Damaged Cores of the Fukushima Reactors. Physical Review Letters, 109, 152501; 109, 152501. Retrieved from arXiv.org:1209.2761v1.
65. Veinberg, A. & Vigner, E. (1961). Physical theory of nuclear reactors. Moscow: Foreign Languages Publishing House.
66. Bartolomei, G.G., Bat, G.A., Baibakov, B.D., & Alkhutov, M.S. (1989). Fundamentals of the theory and methods for calculating nuclear power reactors. Moscow: Energoatomizdat.
67. Feinbrg, S.M., Shykhov, S.B., & Troianskii, B.V. (1978). Theory of nuclear reactors, vol.1. Moscow: Atomizdat.
68. Abagian, P.L., Bazaziants, N.O., Nikolaev, M.N., & Tsybulia, A.M. (1981). Group constants for the calculation of reactors and protection. Moscow: Energoizdat.
69. Ukraintsev, V.F. (2000). Reactivity effects in power reactors. Obninsk: IATE, 2000.
70. Fedorov, N.D. (1961). Brief reference book of the engineer-physicist. Nuclear physics and atomic physics. Moscow: State publishing house of literature in the field of atomic science and technology.
71. Vladimirov, V.I. (1986). Practical tasks on the nuclear reactors operation. Moscow: Energoatomizdat.
72. Kesker, G. (1986). Nuclear energy. Moscow: Energoatomizdat.
73. Neeb, H. (1997). The radiochemistry of nuclear power plants with light water reactors. Berlin, New York: Walter de Gruyter.
74. Samoilov, O.B., Usynin, G.B., & Bakhmetiev, A.M. (1989). Safety of nuclear power plants. Moscow: Energoatomizdat.
75. Safety and security of commercial spent nuclear fuel storage: public report. (2006). Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press.
76. Kabakchi, S.A., & Bulgakov, G.P. (197). Radiation Chemistry in the Nuclear Fuel Cycle. Moscow: MUCT.
77. Skalozubov, V.I., Oborskii, G.A., Kozlov, I.L., Vashchenko, V.N. et al. (2013). A set of methods for reassessing the nuclear energy safety in Ukraine, taking into account the lessons of environmental disasters in Chernobyl and Fukushima. Odesa: Astroprint.
78. Bernstein, A., Wang, Y., Gratta, G., & West, T. (2002). Nuclear reactor safeguards and monitoring with antineutrino detectors. Journal of Applied Physics, 91 (7), 4672.